

Condensations of Levulinic Acid with Aldehydes.

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In the present investigation condensations of levulinic acid with various aldehydes have been systematically studied; and as a result, three distinct types (α , β and δ) of condensation products have been obtained, the last two of these giving rise to interesting ring-compounds on further condensation.

Levulinic acid yielded β -condensation products with benzaldehyde (Erdman, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 3441) and with furfuraldehyde (Erdman and Kehrler, *Ber.*, 1898, 26, 345) in the presence of fused sodium acetate. Erdman's β -benzylidenelevulinic acid (m.p. 125°) has now been obtained much more easily and in much greater yield using dry hydrochloric acid gas as the condensing agent. Similar β -condensations with other aldehydes in presence of the acid at the ordinary temperature have also been systematically studied.

By condensing levulinic acid with benzaldehyde (Erlenmeyer, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 74), furfuraldehyde (Ludwig and Kehrler, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 276) and isobutylaldehyde (Meigash, *Monatsh.*, 1905, 26, 2675) in the presence of dilute caustic soda solution δ -condensation products were previously obtained. Similar δ -condensations with different aldehydes have now further been studied.

Borsche (*Ber.*, 1915, 48, 842) observed that when the sodium salt of the acid is heated with benzaldehyde in the presence of acetic anhydride, the reaction takes place at the α -position. Similar α -condensation products have been obtained by the condensation of levulinic acid with different aldehydes.

$\alpha\beta$ -, $\alpha\delta$ - and $\beta\delta$ -condensations have also been successfully effected in many cases with the formation of dibenzylidene compounds by carrying out the reaction successively with different condensing agents.

Studies of these dibenzylidene compounds have proved very useful in obtaining further evidence of the condensations taking place in different positions with different condensing agents. Thus the identical $\beta\delta$ -dibenzylidene compound, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{C}(\text{:CHPh})\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ is obtained by condensing a second molecule of benzaldehyde either

with β -benzylidenelevulinic acid in presence of caustic soda or with δ -benzylidenelevulinic acid in presence of dry hydrochloric acid gas. But the dibenzylidene derivative, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{C}(\text{:CH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2)\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ obtained from β -nitrobenzylidenelevulinic acid and benzaldehyde in the presence of caustic soda is not identical but isomeric with the compound $\text{NO}_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{C}(\text{:CHPh})\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ obtained from δ -nitrobenzylidenelevulinic acid and benzaldehyde in the presence of dry hydrochloric acid gas.

The $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tribenzylidene compound has also been prepared by condensing the sodium salt of $\beta\delta$ -dibenzylidenelevulinic acid with benzaldehyde in presence of acetic anhydride.

A study of these condensations shows that the hydrogen atoms attached to the β -carbon atom are most reactive while those attached to the α -carbon atom react least readily.

The β - and δ -condensation products (Table I) have also afforded excellent opportunities of studying the possibilities of ring-formation by the action of suitable dehydrating agents; thus, using acetic anhydride, several interesting naphthalene derivatives (Table II) have been obtained from the β -condensation products (*cf.* Erdman, *Ber.*, 1889, 21, 695, who obtained 3-aceto-1-naphthol from β -benzylidenelevulinic acid).

The δ -condensation products under similar circumstances have yielded a new type of cyclic compounds (Table III) which may be looked upon as being formed by the coalescence of an eight-membered ring with a benzene nucleus, thus:

This compound is insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution (cold or hot) indicating the absence of free carboxyl group; it gives a mono-phenylhydrazone proving the presence of carbonyl group; its olefinic character is shown by the ready decolorisation of bromine and alkaline permanganate solutions. These facts support the formula (II) for the substance. It is, however, moderately soluble in caustic soda solution in the cold which is presumably due to its tautomerisation to the enolic form (III) as is supported by the formation of a dibenzoyl derivative. This compound also gives a dinitro-derivative. Further studies of this new type of ring-compounds are in progress.

It is interesting to note that when there is an acidic group (NO_2 or OH) in the *m*-position to the aldehyde group, ring formation takes place much more readily; thus δ -*m*-nitrobenzylidene levulinic acid gives the *cyclooctene* derivative at about 100° whereas the corresponding unsubstituted benzylidene compound requires heating up to $120\text{-}30^\circ$.

This is further corroborated by the action of *m*-hydroxy- and *m*-nitro-benzaldehydes on levulinic acid in presence of dry hydrochloric acid gas when β -condensation takes place followed by ring closure, naphthalene derivatives being obtained at once.

It is remarkable, however, that similar ready ring-formation is also noticed in condensations with piperonal, vanillin and furfuraldehyde, a coumarone derivative being formed in the last case.

o-Hydroxyaldehydes invariably give seven-membered lactones (Table IV) when condensed with levulinic acid in presence of dry hydrochloric acid gas (β -condensation).

The product is insoluble in cold sodium bicarbonate solution and gives a monophenylhydrazone and a dibromo-derivative. On the other hand, five-membered lactones (Δ^2 -angelic lactone derivatives)

are obtained from the δ -condensation products from salicyl- and cinnamic aldehydes.

Both the compounds are insoluble in cold sodium bicarbonate solution and do not react with phenylhydrazine: the former gives the usual ferric chloride reaction.

It is interesting to note that these lactones are all coloured compounds, the seven-membered lactones possessing deeper colour and also exhibiting marked dyeing properties.

Glucose gives a six-membered lactone when condensed with levulinic acid, through β -condensation:

EXPERIMENTAL.

Open-chain Compounds.

β -Benzylidenelevulinic Acid.—Dry hydrochloric acid gas is passed into a mixture of levulinic acid (5.7 g.) and benzaldehyde (5.3 g.) cooled in ice, for about half an hour and the whole is left for a week when a pitch-like substance separates. This is dissolved in caustic soda solution and precipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid; the yellow product washed with water and then with very dilute alcohol. It is finally crystallised from hot dilute alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 125°, and is found to be identical with Erdman's compound (*loc. cit.*) (yield 70%). (Found: C, 70.62; H, 5.9. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.59; H, 5.89 per cent.).

$\beta\delta$ -Dibenzylidenelevulinic Acid.— β -Benzylidenelevulinic acid (7 g.) and benzaldehyde (6 g.) in 25 c.c. of alcohol and 10 c.c. caustic soda (15 %) are heated on the water-bath for about 2 hours and then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold. The precipitate is washed with hot water, then with dilute alcohol and ether and finally crystallised from acetone; it is a yellow micro-crystalline powder, m.p. 146°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone and chloroform but insoluble in water, ether, benzene, carbon disulphide and carbon tetrachloride (yield, 30%). (Found: C, 77.51; H, 5.19. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.48 per cent.).

$\alpha\beta$ -Dibenzylidenelevulinic Acid.—A mixture of dry sodium salt of β -benzylidenelevulinic acid (1.5 g.) and benzaldehyde (0.8 g.) is heated with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) on the water-bath for about 20 hours and poured into water; on adding a little alcohol a yellow solid separates out. This is digested with sodium bicarbonate solution, the filtrate acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitate crystallised from hot absolute alcohol, when golden-yellow needles are obtained melting at 240°, soluble in acetone and chloroform; they are sparingly soluble in cold alcohol and insoluble in carbon tetrachloride, carbon disulphide, ether, benzene and water (yield, 25%). (Found: C, 77.32; H, 5.30. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.48 per cent.).

$\delta\beta$ -Dibenzylidenelevulinic Acid.—Dry hydrochloric acid gas is passed into a mixture of an alcoholic solution of Erlenmeyer's δ -benzylidenelevulinic acid (1.5 g.) and of benzaldehyde (1 g.) cooled in ice, and the whole is left for 10 days. The entire mass is then poured into water, the precipitate collected, washed with water, dilute alcohol and ether and finally crystallised from acetone. It is a yellow micro-crystalline powder, m.p. 146°, which is found to be identical with $\beta\delta$ -dibenzylidenelevulinic acid described before. (yield, 40%). (Found: C, 77.67; H, 5.42. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.48 per cent.).

$\alpha\delta$ -Dibenzylidenelevulinic acid has also been prepared by heating a mixture of dry sodium salt of δ -benzylidenelevulinic acid (1.5 g.) and benzaldehyde (1 g.) with acetic anhydride on the water-bath for about 20 hours, the substance being isolated and purified in the same way as the $\alpha\beta$ -dibenzylidene acid. It forms light yellow needles m.p. 177°, from hot alcohol (yield, 25–30%). (Found: C, 77.3; H, 5.72. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.48 per cent.).

$\alpha\beta$ -Tribenzylidenelevulinic Acid.—A mixture of dry sodium salt of $\beta\delta$ -dibenzylidenelevulinic acid (9 g.) and benzaldehyde (1 g.) is heated with acetic anhydride (10-12 c.c.) on the water-bath for about 24 hours and poured into dilute alcohol when a yellow solid separates. This is washed with water, dilute alcohol and finally crystallised from acetone. The yellow micro-crystalline powder, melting above 240° , is soluble in alcohol and acetone, sparingly soluble in chloroform and insoluble in water, ether, benzene, carbon disulphide etc. (yield, 20%). (Found: C, 79.96; H, 5.62. $C_{26}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 80.23; H, 5.83 per cent.).

Other open-chain compounds obtained by condensing levulinic acid with different aldehydes, together with their derivatives are listed in Table I.

Naphthalene Derivatives.

3-Aceto-7-nitro-1-naphthol. — β -*p*-Nitrobenzylidenelevulinic acid (1 g.) is heated with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) for 3-4 hours at 130 - 140° . The whole mass is poured into a dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate, cooled with ice and left overnight. The red mass which separates is washed repeatedly with hot water and dilute alcohol and is crystallised from acetone in red micro-crystals, m.p. 189° , which are soluble in acetone, sodium bicarbonate or caustic soda, slightly soluble in alcohol and chloroform but insoluble in water, ether, benzene, etc., and give colouration with ferric chloride (yield, 40%). (Found: N, 6.51. $C_{12}H_9O_4N$ requires N, 6.67 per cent.).

Similar naphthalene derivatives and a coumarone are described in Table II.

New Cyclic Compounds.

Benzo-1:4-dikato- Δ^5 : δ -cyclo-octene (II) or Benzo-1:4-dihydrozy-cyclo-octatetrene (III) from Erlenmeyer's δ -Benzylidenelevulinic Acid.— δ -Benzylidenelevulinic acid (2 g.) is heated with acetic anhydride (10-12 c.c.) at 140 - 150° for about 4 hours. The entire mass is poured into a very dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate, cooled with ice and left overnight; a red mass that separates is washed repeatedly with hot water and recrystallised from acetone. The red micro-crystals melt at 196° ; they are soluble in acetone and chloroform, slightly soluble in alcohol, insoluble in benzene, ether, unaffected by sodium bicarbonate solution cold or hot but dissolve in cold

caustic alkalis. (yield, 40%). (Found: C, 76.95; H, 4.98. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 77.42; H, 5.88 per cent.).

Hydrazone.—An acetic acid solution of the above substance is heated with phenylhydrazone on the water-bath for half an hour. The solution is then cooled and poured into ice; the yellow solid that separates is washed with chloroform and ether and recrystallised from hot alcohol. At 100° the monohydrazone is always formed even if the time of heating is extended. (Found: N, 9.96. $C_{18}H_{10}N_2O$ requires N, 10.15 per cent.).

Nitro-derivative.—A dinitro-derivative is obtained when glacial acetic acid solution of the substance is treated with concentrated nitric acid at—8 to—10°. Yellow micro-crystals are obtained by recrystallising from hot alcohol (constitution under investigation). (Found: N, 10.11. $C_{12}H_8O_6N_2$ requires N, 10.15 per cent.).

The *dibenzoyl*-derivative is prepared by Schotten-Baumann process and crystallised from alcohol as light yellow powder melting at 160°, soluble in alcohol and acetone but insoluble in ether, chloroform, etc. (Found: C, 79.97; H, 8.99. $C_{26}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 79.18; H, 4.57 per cent.).

Other cyclic compounds of this type are included in Table III.

Lactones.

β -Salicyl-levulinic lactone.—Dry hydrochloric acid gas is passed into a mixture of levulinic acid (5 g.) and salicylaldehyde (5 g.) for about half an hour and the whole is allowed to stand overnight, when it solidifies *en masse*. The solid is washed with water, very dilute alcohol and ether and finally crystallised from hot alcohol. The reddish-violet micro-crystals, m.p. 151°, are soluble in alcohol, acetone but insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform, etc., unaffected with cold sodium bicarbonate solution though soluble in hot bicarbonate or cold caustic soda (yield almost quantitative). (Found: C, 71.01; H, 4.45. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 71.28; H, 4.89 per cent.).

A *monophenylhydrazone*, melting at 132°, is prepared in the usual manner. (Found: N, 9.37. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.59 per cent.).

A *bromo-derivative* is prepared in the usual manner; pinkish needles melting at 128°. (Found: Br, 44.32. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 44.19 per cent.).

Other lactones are listed in Table IV.

TABLE I.
Open-chain Compounds.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation.	M. p.	Analyses. Calculated. Found. % %	Properties.
β - <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-levulinic acid.	$\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{Ac})\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde + levulinic acid + dry HCl gas at 5°-10° for about half an hour (yield, 50%).	85°	N, 5.62 5.85	Orange needles from hot alcohol.
" Phenylhydrazone	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$	Phenylhydrazine + the substance in acetic acid.	180°	N, 12.98 12.84	Yellow needles from alcohol.
" Dibromo-derivative	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{NBr}_2$	Alcoholic solution of the substance shaken with bromine water.	265°	Br, 39.12 38.99	Light yellow needles from hot dilute alcohol.
β - <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzylidene- δ -benzylidene levulinic acid	$\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}=\text{C}(\text{OO}^i\text{CH}=\text{CHPh})\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	β - <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-levulinic acid + benzaldehyde + 16% KOH (7.8 c.c.) on the water-bath for two hours (yield, 40%).	124°	N, 4.15 3.99	Yellow micro-crystalline powder. The identical compound is obtained from δ -benzylidene-levulinic acid + <i>p</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde + HCl gas.
β - <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzylidene- α -benzylidenelevulinic acid.	$\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}=\text{C}^i\text{Ac}$ O = CHPh CO ₂ H	Sodium salt of β - <i>p</i> -nitrobenzylidene levulinic acid + benzaldehyde + acetic anhydride on the water-bath for 20 hours (yield 55%).	280°	N, 4.15 3.74	Yellow needles from hot absolute alcohol.

<i>δ</i> - <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-levulinic acid	$\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde + levulinic acid + 18% NaOH on water-bath for two hours (yield, 50%).	240°	N, 5-63	5-32	Light orange plates from acetone.
Phenylhydrazone	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHNH}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	In the usual manner.	251°	N, 12-38	12-42	The hydrazone at once changes to a pyrazolone derivative (as it responds to Knorr's reaction.)
Dibromo-derivative	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br}_2\text{NHNH}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	" "	269°	Br, 39-12	38-98	" "
<i>δ</i> - <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-benzylidenelevulinic acid.	$\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{C}(\text{OH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H})\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	<i>δ</i> - <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzylidene levulinic acid + benzaldehyde + dry HCl gas (yield, 30-40%).	167°	N, 4-15	3-98	Light red plates from acetone.
<i>δ</i> - <i>m</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-levulinic acid.	$\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde + levulinic acid + 15% NaOH (yield, 40%)	254°	N, 5-62	5-61	Yellow powder; decolorises bromine.
Hydrazone	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHNH}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	In the usual manner	—	N, 12-38	12-21	Yellow powder.
Bromo-derivative	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Br}_2\text{NHNH}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	" "	—	Br, 39-12	98-98	Red powder.
Indigo		<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde + levulinic acid + 15-20% NaOH	—	N, 10-67	10-74	Yield is only 5%.
<i>δ</i> - <i>o</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-levulinic acid.	$\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{OH})\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	" (yield, 80%)	169°	N, 5-62	5-11	Light red powder (constitution under investigation). Does not give indigo on treatment with alkali.

TABLE I.—continued.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation.	M.p.	Analyses.		Properties.
				Calculated.	Found.	
<i>p</i> -o-Nitrobenzylidenelevulinic acid.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{OOCH}_3 \\ \\ \text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{C} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde + levulinic acid + dryHCl gas (yield, 60%)	121°	N, 5.62	5.46	Grey micro-crystals from alcohol; decolorises bromine water; gives a hydrazone (m.p. 92°).
<i>β</i> -o-Nitrobenzylidene- <i>β</i> -benzylidenellevulinic acid	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CHPh} \\ \\ \text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{C} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$	In the usual manner (yield, 40%)	157°	N, 4.15	4.14	Yellow micro-crystalline powder from acetone.
<i>β</i> -Cinnamyllevulinic acid.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{C} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$	Cinnamic aldehyde + levulinic acid + dryHCl gas (yield, 80%)	115°	C, 78.04 H, 6.09	78.90 5.97	Orange plates from hot alcohol.
„ Dibromo-derivative (according to Thiele's theory)	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{Br}_2$	In the usual manner.	—	Br, 41.08	41.02	Light yellow plates.
„ Phenylhydrazone	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$	„ „	186°	N, 8.75	8.53	Light red needles from alcohol.

β -Cinnamyl- β -benzylidenellevulinic acid	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}=\text{OHPb} \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\cdot\text{CH}=\text{C} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$	" (yield 40%) "	112°	C, 79.24 H, 5.88	79.04 5.78	Yellow needles from acetone.
β -Cinnamyl	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \\ \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$	Ommamic aldehyde + levulinic acid + 15% NaOH (yield, 60%)	161°	C, 79.04 H, 6.08	79.89 6.07	Yellow needles; gives a hydrazone and decolorises bromine water.
β -Anisal	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{CH}_3\text{O}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}=\text{C} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$	Anisaldehyde + levulinic acid + dry HCl gas (yield, 60%)	58°	C, 66.67 H, 5.98	66.09 5.82	Red needles from alcohol; reacts with phenylhydrazine; decolorises bromine water; very hygroscopic.
β -Citral	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}=\text{C} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$	Citral + levulinic acid + dry HCl gas (yield, 25%)	187°	C, 67.42 H, 8.91	68.82 8.48	Orange-yellow powder from acetone.
β -Vanillin	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \\ \\ (\text{OH})(\text{CH}_3)\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$	Vanillin + levulinic acid + dilute NaOH (yield, 25-30%)	275°	C, 69.1 H, 5.6	61.51 5.37	Rose-red powder from alcohol; reacts with phenylhydrazine; decolorises bromine water.
β -Salicyl	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \\ \\ (\text{OH})\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{OH} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$	Salicylaldehyde + levulinic acid + dilute NaOH (yield 55%)	166°	C, 65.45 H, 5.45	64.96 5.28	Grayish brown powder; if however strong HCl is used to acidify, lactone is at once formed.
β - <i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzylidenelevulinic acid	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CH}=\text{C} \\ \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H} \end{array}$	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde + levulinic acid + dry HCl gas (yield 60%)	160°	C, 65.45 H, 5.45	65.05 5.41	Light red powder; reacts with phenylhydrazine, and decolorises bromine water.

TABLE I.—Continued.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation.	M.p.	Analyses, Calculated. Found.	Properties.
<i>o</i> - <i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzylidene levulinic acid	$\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde + levulinic acid + dilute NaOH (yield, 25%)	109°	C, 65.45 H, 5.45	65.02 5.11 Yellow plates from hot dilute alcohol.
<i>o</i> - <i>m</i> -	"	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde + levulinic acid + dilute NaOH (yield, 30%)	110°	C, 65.45 H, 5.45	64.95 5.98 Dull red powder.
<i>o</i> -Resorcyldenelevu- lino acid	$(\text{OH})_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{CH}=\text{CH}\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$	1 : 2 : 4-Resorcylddehyde + levulinic acid + dilute NaOH (yield, 40%)	261°	C, 61.03 H, 5.08	61.07 5.11 Brown powder from hot alcohol; decolorises bro- mine and reacts with phenylhydrazine;

TABLE II.

Naphthalene Derivatives.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation.	M.p.	Analyses, Calculated. Found.	Properties.
3-Aceto-6-(or 8)-nitro-1 naphthol.	I, NO, in 6 or 8 position	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde + levulinic + dry HCl (see at 0°-5° (yield 35%)).	163°	N, 8.07 6.49	6.49 Red plates from acetone, insoluble in cold or hot Na-bicarbonate but soluble in NaOH.

3-Aceto-5-nitro-	I, NO ₂ in 5-position	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzylidene-levulinic acid + acetic anhydride at 120-130° for 6 to 7 hours. (yield, 60%).	220°	N, 6.07	6.59	Brown micro-crystalline powder from acetone.
3-Aceto-7-methoxy	I, OMe in 7-position	β -Anisal-levulinic acid + acetic anhydride at 140-145° for 4-5 hours (yield, 60%).	164°	C, 72.22 H, 5.55	71.96 5.42	Red powder soluble in caustic acids; insoluble in cold or hot bicarbonate; slight coloration with FeCl ₃ .
3-Aceto-7 : 8 (or 6 : 7)- dioxymethylene	I, O(CH ₂) ₂ ; in 6 : 7- or 7 : 8-position.	Piperonal + levulinic acid + dry HCl gas at 0°.5° (yield, 50%).	234°	C, 67.83 H, 4.35	67.26 4.31	Flaky crystals of chocolate colour; insoluble in Na ₂ -bicarbonate soluble in NaOH; reacts with phenylhydrazine and benzaldehyde.
3-Aceto-7-hydroxy-8 (or 6)-methoxy-1-naphthol	I, OH in 7, OMe in 8- or 6-position	Vanillin + levulinic acid + dry HCl gas at 5°.10°. (yield 60%)	169°	C, 71.28 H, 5.59	67.2 5.19	Reddish powder, soluble in NaOH; insoluble in Na ₂ -bicarbonate; reacts with phenylhydrazine.
3-Aceto-6 (or 8)-hydroxy	I, OH in 6 (or 8)-position	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde + levulinic acid + dry HCl gas at 0°.5°. (yield, 60%) Formaldehyde + levulinic acid + dry HCl gas at 0°.5°. (yield, 70%)	164°	C, 71.28 H, 4.89	70.83 4.61	Brown powder, insoluble in Na ₂ -bicarbonate but dissolves in NaOH; gives an oxime.
6-Aceto-1-oxycoumarone			190°	C, 68.75 H, 4.54	67.92 4.52	Identical with Eirdmann's compound.

TABLE III.
Benzo-cyclo-octatetrens Derivatives.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation.	M. p.	Analyses.	Properties.
				Calculated.	Found.
Benzo-9-nitro-1,4-dihydroxy-cyclo-octatetrene	III, NO ₂ in position 9	<i>o</i> -p-Nitrobenzylidene-levulinic acid + acetic anhydride at about 140° for 3-4 hours.	210°	N, 6.07 6.41	Micro-crystalline powder from acetone; insoluble in NaHCO ₃ (cold or hot), soluble in NaOH; reacts with phenylhydrazine; decolorises bromine; no reaction on FeCl ₃ .
Benzo-6(or 10)-nitro "	III, NO ₂ in position 8 or 10	<i>o</i> -m-Nitrobenzylidene-levulinic acid + acetic anhydride on water-bath for 5 hours.	236°	N, 6.07 6.39	Brown powder from acetone. Properties same as those of the preceding one.
Benzo-9-aceto-1-hydroxy "	III, H in place of OH in position 4 and COOH ₂ in position 9 ₂	<i>β</i> -Cinnamyl-levulinic acid + acetic anhydride at 180°-140° for about 4 hours.	230°	C, 79.24 H, 5.06 6.78-86 5.49	Red plates from acetone. Properties similar.
Benzo-9-methoxy-1,4-dihydroxy- "	III ₂ OMe in position 9 ₂	<i>o</i> -Anisal-levulinic acid + acetic anhydride for 4 to 5 hours.	79°	C, 72.22 H, 5.55 5.45	Red plates. Properties similar.
Benzo-9-hydroxy-1,4-dihydroxy- "	III, OH in position 9 ₂	<i>o</i> -p-Hydroxybenzylidene-levulinic acid + acetic anhydride at 140° for 4-5 hours.	246°	C, 71.97 H, 4.89 7.0-88 4.43	Light red powder. Properties similar.

TABLE IV.

Lactones.

Name.	Formula.	M. P.	Analyses.		Properties.
			Calculated.	Found.	
Cinnamylangelic lactone.	VI.	Above 260°	C, 79.24 H, 5.66	78.5 5.62	Grayish-red powder; insoluble in cold NaHCO ₃ , dissolves when hot; does not give hydrazone.
β -Resorcyll-levulinic lactone.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \cdot \text{CH} = \text{C} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{O} - \text{CO} - \text{CH}_2 \end{array}$	Above 210°	C, 66.06 H, 4.58	65.59 4.46	Bluish-violet powder; dyes silk a violet shade; insoluble in hot bicarbonate but not in the cold; reacts with PhNHNH ₂ .
δ -Salicylangelic lactone.	V.	169°	C, 71.28 H, 4.89	70.84 4.68	Grayish-brown powder; gives coloration with FeCl ₃ ; does not react with PhNHNH ₂ ; reacts with hot Na-bicarbonate
β -Naphthyl-levulinic lactone.	$\begin{array}{c} \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{CH} = \text{C} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \\ \\ \text{O} - \text{CO} - \text{CH}_2 \end{array}$	94°	C, 76.18 H, 4.38	75.91 4.5	Brown powder; insoluble in bicarbonate and in cold NaOH; dyes silk a brown shade, gives a bromo-derivative (m.p. 113°); benzylidene compound (m.p. 112°); reacts with PhNH ₂ NH ₂ .

TABLE IV—continued.

Lactones.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation.	M. P.	Analyses.		Properties.
				Calculated.	Found.	
Along with the above compound, another compound is formed in 20 p. c. yield.	Under investigation.		223°	C, 4'76 H, 75'02	Green powder; insoluble in caustic alkali; decolourises bromine water; does not give a hydrazone.	
Glucoselevulinic lactone.	VII.	Glucose + levulinic acid dry HCl gas (yield, 20%)	96°	C, 50'77 H, 6'15	50'41 5'96	Red micro-crystalline powder; soluble in alcohol, acetone and chloroform; insoluble in cold bicarbonate soluble in caustic alkalis.
.. Tetra-acetyl derivative.		The above lactone + acetic anhydride on water-bath.	260°	C, 53'73 H, 5'67	52'95 5'27	A brown powder.

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